

ICT Driven Education: A Framework For 21st Century Community Development Needs in Nigeria.

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Abstract

This paper on Information, Communication and Technology driven education: a frame work for 21st century community development needs in Nigeria has the following objectives: to determine the need for ICT in education as it enhances teaching and learning and to determine its role in community development needs in Nigeria. The study employed secondary source of methodology and contends that ICT driven education will improve quality of teaching and learning and unravel community citizens' needs of any society for sustainable development. Findings reveal that ICT driven education is inevitable in modernization and development of a sustainable community development needs, improvement on the process of teaching and learning at the formal, semi-formal and non-formal levels of education, enhance change in innovation, creativity and proffer priority for community needs and activities among others. It is discovered that inclusion of ICT driven education for community development needs will reduce educational inequality, increase access to teaching and learning, instill managerial skills, solve personal problems, enhance community development as agent for life activities, needs and programmes and to help meet the aspiration of people within the community when information, communication and technology is implemented in all educational levels of the society. Therefore, the study concludes that technology driven education for community development needs will help create socio-economic development of the country through knowledge based-society through acquisition of new skills and being economical active.

Keywords: ICT, Education, Community, Community Development Needs, 21st Century.

Introduction

Education is not only meant to serve as a custodian of the peoples' culture expressed in the language they speak, mode of dress, marriages, social organization, political activities and technology. It also enhances the community development of societies. Education serves as a bridge that links an individual and his community, reduces unemployment and enhances community development. Seya (2014) adduced that investment in the development of human capital through education is crucial for developing a labour force and managerial know-how able to compete to today's global economy. The 21st century Information and Communication Technology (ICT)

driven education is attached to the changing technological world, which is inevitable in modernization and development of a sustainable community development needs. The 21st century brought a new innovation in the transformation of the world. Despite the historical, scientific and technological revolutions, it enhanced the pedestal of change, innovation, dynamism, creativity and proffered priority for community needs and activities, Oji and Okemini (2022). The changes in information and communication technology have also improved the process of teaching and learning at the formal, semi-formal and non-formal levels of education. Education in its entirety instills managerial skills to beneficiaries which enable them to organize, consult, manage, evaluate, implement and solve their personal needs and prioritize community development needs for community wellbeing.

Development can only be made possible if it is human centered process and this can be achieved through ICT driven education. Omona (2020) states that information in the 21st century is regarded as one of the most fundamental right requirements for personal and social development, and for citizens' engagement in effective governance. Effective ICT services enhance socio-economic development by creating a knowledge-based society and empowering people, especially marginalized people (rural citizens) and those living in poverty to exercise their rights, be economically active, learn new skills, enrich cultural identity and take part in decision making process. International Federation for Libraries Association (IFLA, 2013b) therefore, states that community development is an approach for improvement that is geared towards the upliftment of community members to a better living by solving the community needs. Nwankwo (2011) believes that community development means better living both materially and socially. It is a process where people are taught to improve themselves not only by doing things together but also by planning together with a view to providing the actual technique for doing the job or finding suitable solution to their problems. In this circumstance therefore, ICT driven education has enhanced community development to be conceptualized as a change process causing improvement to life activities, needs and programs, and social relations that aim to meeting the needs and aspiration of people with similar historical and cultural heritage living together in a community (Bello 2022). It is in view of these that the crux of the paper is to find out how technological driven education has enhanced community development needs in the 21st century Nigeria.

Concept of ICT Driven Education in Nigeria

Visibility, accessibility, and relevant to the 21st century have made education and educational stakeholders to embrace and incorporate information and communication technology education (ICT) in adult learners and facilitators in order to meet community development needs. Abraham and Chuku (2018) state that ICT is a system derived from intermingling of information technology (IT) and communication technology (CT). In furtherance, it is defined as the application of electronic media, computers, telecommunication gadgets, digital media, and mobile devices, personal digital assistants (PDAs) in the acquisition, processing, storage, retrieving, and dissemination of information. Abraham and Bariyaa (2020) opt that ICT is a terminology for information and communication system which refers to technology used for collecting, storing, editing, and passing on of information in various forms to improve education and enhance adult community development needs and participation.

Information and Communication Technology in education refers to the technology that involves using electronic devices to transmit data, graphics, symbols, sounds, videos, messages, and pictures to achieve specific and broad educational goals and objectives. The expectation informed

the need for appropriate technological platform to adequately communicate, interact or interfere with the adult learners and transmit their progress or challenges to the facilitators or change agents at the comfort of their homes and offices. This will enhance adult learning, improve their participations and streamline community development needs.

ICT driven education is a transmission of basic skills and concepts that form the foundation of higher order thinking skills and creativity which is enhanced by ICT through drill and practice. It is in this premise that Haddad and Draxier (2002) state that ICT contributed to effective learning through expanding access, promoting efficiency and improving the quality of learning and management system for community wellbeing and development. In another development, Obeng in Agbetuyi and Oluwatayo (2012) believe that ICT is now a utility such as water and electricity and hence has become a major role in education, learning and research in general, health and poverty alleviation by generating or creating new jobs and investment opportunities.

However, most adult learning centers and even formal schools are still gambling with analogue and laborious task of manual registration of students, maintenance of performance and achievements amongst others. Consequently, the 21st century education is geared towards total shift from manual teaching and learning to technological driven teaching and learning in both the formal and non- formal educational system. The shift from analogue to technology and to technological driven method of education is what Abraham and Chuku (2018) opt that the 21st century education emphasizes a technological- based education that is problem solving which in a short while promotes community wellbeing and development. Modern day adult facilitators, stakeholders and change agents must be knowledgeable in ICT in order to meet the global changes in education and learning.

Ultimate power of technology in education is the information and the communication. ICT is paramount for social life, business, education and economy, to meet the demands of modern information society, and for the progress of education and human development (Aduwa-Ogiegbaen & Iyamu, 2005). Therefore, modern day teachers, adult facilitators, stakeholders and change agents must be knowledgeable in ICT in order to meet the global changes in education, teaching and learning.

Accordingly, Balogun in Yusuf and Balogun (2011) states that the use of ICT in education improves the quality and quantity of education and causes better innovative, creative and cognitive thinking, higher productivity, efficiency, and better educational outcome. Information and Communication Technology facilitates both instructional and learning process and has a great influence on teaching and learning at educational institutions. It provides opportunity for personalized, flexible and asynchronous learning and shifts the learning from teacher centered to students centered and, hence, a catalyst for reforms about classroom, educational institute, and community needs and system development (Youssef & Dahmani, 2008). UNESCO (2014) insists that ICT enhances the learning of the students, help the students to learn new skill sets, promote social mobility, help the citizens to compete in a worldwide economy and thus has a multiplier effect across the education system. Hence, ICT becomes an invaluable mechanism that drives the 21st century education toward community development needs and societal wellbeing.

Community Development Needs in the 21st Century Nigeria

Community can be classified as the structure of relationship through which a localized population meets its daily requirements. It is a mechanism through which the population organizes itself for survival in a particular living environment. Community development therefore, becomes a mutual

understanding and cooperation within and among people of the same community or society to work harmoniously (Okafor, 2022). Furthermore, it is a process where the efforts of community citizens are combined with that of the governmental authorities to improve the living standard of the rural people. It is this harmonious participation and engagement of community people that Frank and Smith (2013) believe that it is a process where community members come together to identify their needs, take collective actions and generate solutions to community problems within the community frame work, knowledge and skill.

Therefore, community development needs in the 21st century varies from one community to the other among which are: healthcare service, poverty reduction, literacy education, women/youth empowerment, vocational training and skill acquisition, food security, cooperative societies, leadership accountability among others.

These community development needs may vary depending on a particular community as no two communities have the same needs. However, they provide a comprehensive framework for understanding 21st century community development needs. ICT has become a global phenomenon of great importance and concerns in all aspects of human endeavor, spanning across education, governance, business, labour, market, shares, productivity, trade, agriculture, commerce and recently community development needs.

ICT Driven Education for Community Development Needs in Nigeria

Healthcare Services: The most significant tool for development is health. It is therefore one of the cardinal required basic social needs of the rural communities. This is because health services have the driving force for community development of any nation. In view of the importance of community health and development, Ibama and Dennis (2016) believe that community health and natural development are inextricably tied together, in which the evaluation of natural development cannot be completed without the community health component. ICT as a medium of information would play prominent role in dissemination, mobilization and conscientization of the community citizens on the need to provide community health services, mobile clinics among others.

Literacy Education: Literacy education is an inseparable part of development and the rights of every citizen. ICT in education will create the enabling environment where citizens will learn at the comfort of their homes or offices. It will reduce face to face teaching and learning method and provide unlimited access to knowledge. It enhances the ability of every individual to acquire the skills of reading, writing, and computation which will transform and mobilize them to participate actively in their self-help projects which increases national development. According to Imhabekhai (2009) the desire and ability to read, write, and compute materials promote productivity and enhance development in any society. It enables the recipients to understand higher concepts of developmental needs and programmes which maintain a sustainable community development.

Education: The 21st century basic community development need is education. Education according to Gbesoevi (2019) is a process of training and developing knowledge, skill, mind and character of people. It is a process where the latent abilities of individuals are developed so that they can be useful to themselves and the community at large. Aka and Onoyima (2022) adduced that the use of emerging ICT tools, platforms and devices has become an integral part of education in which case educators and students had to rely on the use of various technological devices, platforms and tools like videoconferencing tools and e-learning platforms to aid continued education online. Spector (2012) states that the emerging ICT provide opportunities for educators to improve their skills and job performances as it introduces flexibility to teaching and learning

process, and takes teaching and learning beyond the physical classrooms and face-to-face methodology.

Skill Acquisition: Community as a rural setting is confronted with numerous challenges ranging on how to acquire skills in order to reduce dependency and poverty. Therefore community vocational educational need is tailored toward the context that at the end of the training all the participants must have acquired a skill which will enable them enhance self-sustaining and, or improve their productivity where such a participant is employed. This is the assertion of Egunu, Akpotohwo and Ogeibiri in Okafor and Okafor (2024) where they maintained that vocational education for skill acquisition is designed to prepare citizens for an occupation, a trade or a job. ICT in education is a catalyst which plays prominent roles in skill acquisition and vocational training. It is a machine that enhances and propels individuals towards skill acquisition and self-reliant. In agreement with the role of ICT, Daniju (2017) states that the best option for empowerment is skill acquisition as it will ensure financial independence, self-sufficient and a better standard of living. It will equally bring about social empowerment by providing jobs, develop entrepreneurial ability which in turn will ensure financial independence and assure community development participation.

Empowerment: Empowerment is being economically self-reliant and independent. Aka and Onoyima (2022) opt that empowerment is the degree of autonomy and self-determination in people and in communities. It enables the citizens represent their interest in a responsible and self-determined way, acting on their own authority. In another development, Oji (2014) insists that empowerment is beyond participation. He argued that it implies enabling people to understand the reality of their environment, reflect on the factors shaping that environment and take steps to effect changes to improve the situation and their wellbeing. Thus, ICT empowerment of individuals can be in form of active participation and involvement in an organization, it also involves collective decision making and shared leadership at the community level. In this instance, jobs are created.

Cooperative societies: Cooperative societies are important tools for real transformation and development of rural communities. According to Baarda (2006) cooperative societies is a form of collective action in which individuals (rural people) join together to accomplish what would be more costly or impossible to achieve individually. Akpan (2015) insisted that cooperative societies serve as an effective community development vehicle by nature; they build economic self-reliance and development. The community petty traders and artisans could assess loan from the cooperative with little or no collateral. It equally will serve as an employment outfit for the rural people. The benefits of cooperative societies accrue to the larger societies because they create local jobs; reinsure locally, emphasis on skills and education, raises local management capacity, reduce rural-urban migration and concentration on capital for community development, Hossain (2014).

Leadership Accountability: Leadership has been identified as an important function towards achieving the aims and objectives of a community or society. Iheriohanma, Wokoma and Nwokorie (2014) stated that leadership is an “essential oil that keeps the wheel of government working without any difficulty”. Community leadership accountability will not only keep the wheel of community governance working, it will build trust among the citizens, enhance respect, participation and engagement, increase rural strategic infrastructure, reduce unnecessary public expenditure and build confidence among the citizens. Community leaders should possess the greatest knowledge, understanding of their community development needs and have the agility, creativity and energy to propel motivation, mobilization and so achieve development.

Rural Industries: One of the cardinal community development needs of the 21st century is rural industries. Communities can be transformed through rural industries to urban cities and so reduce urban migrations. These could be achieved through Small and Medium-scale Enterprises (SMS) like metal work, potter, hair dressing, tailoring, soap making among others. Bello (2022) states that the role of industries in rural transformation could help to promote self-employment, self-reliant, rural based job opportunities and investments, intensify community development and sustainable wellbeing of the people.

Conclusion

The world has become a global community due to the invention and introduction of technology in all facets of human activities including education. Education at all levels is a catalyst which removes ignorance, eliminates poverty, increases self-reliance and enhances community participation and development of the society. It is inevitable therefore that the 21st century education must be information, communication and technology driven in order to meet community development needs of the 21st century society. In other to achieve community development needs, sustained national development and to meet global educational requirement of the time, ICT in education must be tailored down to cover all educational levels in the country. Therefore, it is imperative that for community development needs to be achieved; ICT must be in cooperated in teaching and learning in all educational levels for effective wellbeing and for the development of the society.

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